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Research Article

**AN INVESTIGATION AND RESEARCH TO CRITERION AND
MEASURE THE LARIUM CONSEQUENCES ON EYEBALL**¹Dr. Muiz Ilahi, ²Dr. MahRukh Khawar, ³Dr. Muhammad Imran¹DHQ Teaching Hospital Gujranwala**Article Received:** November 2020 **Accepted:** December 2020 **Published:** January 2021**Abstract:****Objective:** The objective of this researches is to investigate the consequences of larium on the pictorial complaint.**Victims and methods:** Pictorial field (VF) were taken to conclude the ophthalmic condition and the research confirmed 67 victims with weekly larium treatment (for malaria prevention) for 1 year. Pictorial insight, intraocular pressure (IOP), dilated posterior section.**Results:** The average age of cases is 43.58 (84.05%) are men and 11 (15.94%) are women. Two of 69 victims had Pictorial insight pain and slight smearing. However, none of the shield's changes in the retina, VF, fundus and anterior or posterior section.**Conclusion:** In addition, more research is needed to assess the increased risk of long-term use. There is no risk of blindness after treatment with larium for 1 year.**Key words:** Antimalarial Medicines, Retinal Toxicity, Larium, Presbyopia.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Muiz Ilahi,**

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INTRODUCTION:

In recent research by a recent UN mission, public opinion is likely to see this drug as a harmful drug that damages the retina when it developed and used the legend against the use of larium. Larium is a medicine used to prevent malaria as an alternative medicine, which in recent years is considered to be more consequences than prescriptions and the use of chloroquine. People interested in drug production or victim treatment. This concept may be incorrect, but everyone's primary task is to do more research and research to see if the drug is being used by people and to confirm its usefulness and consequences in saving human life. Retina. Because there is no evidence of the retinal toxicity of this drug, the research was conducted to assess the consequences on the Pictorial apparatus and replace the myth impression. In other studies, on this drug, it has been observed that the use of this drug has negative side consequences in various body tissues, but no specific or specific studies of the side consequences of this drug have been performed since.

VICTIMS AND METHODS:

The research involved 69 cases who received weekly larium treatment for a year. This descriptive research was conducted at the Eyeball Unit-1 Services Hospital

Lahore for 12 months duration from December 2017 to November 2018. Diabetes, hypertension, cataracts, any pre-existing illness or other preventive treatment as well as victims older than 70 years and older were excluded. For the prevention of malaria, larium is administered once a week as a 250 mg tablet. Victims involved in OPD of the eyeball were examined with a slit lamp using Snellen Pictorial insight tables. Subsequently, victims were followed at 3-month intervals for 1 year with larium treatment. Then the slit lamp examined the anterior section along with the tonometry for recording the baseline. The dilated posterior section examination was performed with a 90 D lens and a drop of pilocarpine was administered at the end of the examination. To redefine the negative consequences, the percentage for demographics, glaucoma and pictorial complaint and bottom impact was calculated. The same procedure was followed at each visit.

RESULTS:

There were 58 (84.05%) men and 11 (15.94%) women (Table 1). The corrected Pictorial insight ranges from 6/6 to 6/12. 67 confirmed cases, which underwent weekly treatment with larium for a year, were evaluated.

Table 1: Socio demographic profile of subjects

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Female	11	15.94
Male	58	84.05

The victim's age is 20 to 65 years and the average value is 43 years. 2 (2.89%) of 69 victims with blurred vision and eyeball pain affected Pictorial function. Intraocular pressure ranges between 10-18 mm Hg. The CD ratio is from 0.3 to 0.5. None of them were accompanied by changes in the anterior or posterior section. None of them experienced an increase or decrease in intraocular pressure (Table 2). No VF defects were observed.

Table 2: Distribution of cases according to Pictorial status after 1-year larium treatment

Adverse consequences	Pictorial status affected no of cases	Consequences on Pictorial status cases in %age
Intraocular stress	-	-
Retinal noxiousness	-	-
Eyeball discomfort	2	2.89
Blur visualization	2	2.89

DISCUSSION:

These are doxycycline, larium, proguanil (Malarone), atovaquone, hydroxychloroquine sulfate and chloroquine. Larium is approved by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for the treatment of malaria. There are five drugs approved for the prevention of malaria. Weekly dosing improves compliance with preventive dosing programs. Of

these, only larium, chloroquine and hydroxychloroquine sulfate are stable enough to allow weekly dosing. As a result, larium, doxycycline and atovaquone-proguanil are more often used to prevent malaria⁷. After the prophylaxis of malaria, larium is administered as a 250 mg tablet once a week. Though, the resistance of malaria parasites to chloroquine and hydroxychloroquine sulfate is quite common.

These consequences are more common than prophylaxis at the therapeutic dose, even if there is no malaria. The frequency of adverse events reported following larium administration is variable. Unfortunately, larium is also associated with neurological sequelae such as panic attacks, suicidal thoughts, anxiety, sleep disorders, nightmares, tremor, dizziness, headaches, mood swings and fatigue.

Although long-term use of larium is associated with eyeball damage in rats, retinal disorders were not found in long-term users. Common side consequences of larium include nausea, vomiting, dizziness, insomnia, unusual dreams, hallucinations and blurred vision. Interestingly, in Google searches using the search terms [larium] and [Pictorial field defect], reference was made to malaria chemoprophylaxis describing a victim who received and identified larium for 18 months. Full PubMed studies using the terms [larium] and [eyeball disorder], [retinal disorder] did not reveal important references. Although in our research two victims complained of mild vision and blurred eyeball pain, no detailed anterior or posterior abnormalities were observed in the detailed ophthalmological examination. Recent studies published in this journal report another eyeball disorder associated with optic neuritis among Japanese peace-keeping forces of 1876 who used larium to prevent malaria in Timor-Leste. People with bilateral pigmented epithelial retinal lesions. Unlike our victims, there was no significant change after long-term use of larium.

Neuropsychiatric side consequences are more significant and a wide range of neuropsychiatric symptoms have been previously reported among larium users, including severe depression and acute psychosis. Concerns have been raised about negative consequences resulting from larium prophylaxis. Because our searches and literature studies do not identify a single case of optic neuritis or larium - associated retinopathy, these conditions may be a coincidence, not a result of chemical prevention. Various environmental factors, such as stress associated with international travel, tropical climate or difficult tasks, may also play a role or result from antimalarial activity, but may be particularly larium. However, due to the nature of these negative consequences, causal relationships are often not confirmed. According to earlier data from volunteers of the Peace Force for Energy Efficiency Recently, a non-comparative research reported a high incidence of side consequences among Japanese travelers using larium prophylaxis. However, their severity has not

been explained. It is beneficial for EA to start early because it can allow for an alternative anti-malarial transition before departure. The current research, one of the JSDF studies and expert review, showed that most of the side consequences associated with larium prophylaxis occur during the first few doses and then decrease. Therefore, this drug can now be used and there is no doubt in future studies, and long-term studies are ongoing. In the light of the above discussion, although there have been some negative consequences on human tissues, especially CNS, in various studies during malaria larium prophylaxis, there were no significant side consequences for retina in our research.

CONCLUSION:

More research is needed to assess the increased risk of long-term use. There is no risk of blindness after treatment with larium for 1 year. The use of larium is a safer drug and it has not been found in our studies / studies that it can cause some negative consequences on the eyeballs. However, if the tests continue to achieve results, there will be no harm. However, larium can be safely used up to 01 years under regular supervision and control visits.

REFERENCES:

1. Schneiderman, Aaron I., Yasmin S. Cypel, Erin K. Dursa, and Robert M. Bossarte. "Associations between use of antimalarial medications and health among US veterans of the wars in Iraq and Afghanistan." *The American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene* 99, no. 3 (2018): 638-648.
2. Rangel-Friedman, Gary, and David Steven Haffner. "Systems and methods for delivering an ocular implant to the suprachoroidal space within an eyeball." U.S. Patent 10,188,551, issued January 29, 2019. Rangel-Friedman G, Haffner DS, inventors; Glaukos Corp, assignee. Systems and methods for delivering an ocular implant to the suprachoroidal space within an eyeball. United States patent US 10,188,551. 2019 Jan 29.
3. Berman, Jonathan, Tracey Brown, Geoffrey Dow, and Stephen Toovey. "Tafenoquine and primaquine do not exhibit clinical neurologic signs associated with central nervous system lesions in the same manner as earlier 8-aminoquinolines." *Malaria journal* 17, no. 1 (2018): 1-12.
4. Rangel-Friedman G, Haffner DS, inventors; Glaukos Corp, assignee. Systems and methods for delivering an ocular implant to the suprachoroidal space within an eyeball. United States patent US 10,285,853. 2019 May 14. Rangel-Friedman, Gary, and David S. Haffner. "Systems and

- methods for delivering an ocular implant to the suprachoroidal space within an eyeball." U.S. Patent 10,285,853, issued May 14, 2019.
5. Eberemu, N.C., 2018. VARIATIONS IN HAEMATOLOGICAL FACTORS OF GUINEA PIGS INFECTED AND TREATED WITH DIFFERENT ANTI SCHISTOSOMA TREATMENT. *FUDMA JOURNAL OF SCIENCES-ISSN: 2616-1370*, 1(1), pp.40-48. Eberemu, Nkiru Charity. "VARIATIONS IN HAEMATOLOGICAL FACTORS OF GUINEA PIGS INFECTED AND TREATED WITH DIFFERENT ANTI SCHISTOSOMA TREATMENT." *FUDMA JOURNAL OF SCIENCES-ISSN: 2616-1370* 1, no. 1 (2018): 40-48.
 6. Alshaban, Fouad. "A recommendation for the use of chloroquine, hydroxychloroquine, primaquine, or tafenoquine for prophylaxis against the 2019 novel coronavirus (COVID-19) with note to the ophthalmic considerations." *Eyeball Reports* 6, no. 1 (2020).
 7. Dandu, K., Kallamadi, P.R., Thakur, S.S. and Rao, C.M., 2019. Drug repurposing for retinoblastoma: Recent advances. *Current topics in medicinal chemistry*, 19(17), pp.1535-1544. Dandu, Kamakshi, Prathap R. Kallamadi, Suman S. Thakur, and Ch M. Rao. "Drug repurposing for retinoblastoma: Recent advances." *Current topics in medicinal chemistry* 19, no. 17 (2019): 1535-1544.
 8. Urbano, João Cláudio da Costa, Ranny Beatriz de Carvalho Holanda Leite, Renan Leopoldo Pereira Castro, Clarice Maux Vianna da Silva, Joelma Maria de Araújo Andrade, Cláudio Bruno Silva de Oliveira, Vanessa Santos de Arruda Barbosa, Valter Ferreira de Andrade-Neto, and Cecília Maria de Carvalho Xavier Holanda. "Consequences of toxoplasmic infection on the biodistribution of a brain radiopharmaceutical." *International journal of radiation biology* 95, no. 11 (2019): 1547-1551.
 9. Mahadi, K. M., V. K. Lall, S. A. Deuchars, and J. Deuchars. "Cardiovascular autonomic consequences of transcutaneous auricular nerve stimulation via the tragus in the rat involve spinal cervical sensory afferent pathways." *Brain stimulation* 12, no. 5 (2019): 1151-1158.
 10. Val, F., Costa, F.T., King, L., Brito-Sousa, J.D., Bassat, Q., Monteiro, W.M., Siqueira, A.M., Luzzatto, L. and Lacerda, M.V., 2019. Tafenoquine for the prophylaxis, treatment and elimination of malaria: eagerness must meet prudence. *Future microbiology*, 14(15), pp.1261-1279. Val, Fernando, Fabio TM Costa, Liam King, Jose D. Brito-Sousa, Quique Bassat, Wuelton M. Monteiro, André M. Siqueira, Lucio Luzzatto, and Marcus VG Lacerda. "Tafenoquine for the prophylaxis, treatment and elimination of malaria: eagerness must meet prudence." *Future microbiology* 14, no. 15 (2019): 1261-1279.
 11. Baker, Kendra C., Christy L. Rettenmund, Samantha J. Sander, Anne E. Rivas, Kaitlin C. Green, Lisa Mangus, and Ellen Bronson. "Clinical consequences of hemoparasite infections in snowy owls (*Bubo scandiacus*)." *Journal of Zoo and Wildlife Medicine* 49, no. 1 (2018): 143-152.
 12. Yetunde, Onalapo A., Onalapo Olakunle James, and Adeyeballba Oluwaseyi Adegboyega. "Malaria, Antimalaria Drugs, Drug/Parasite Interactions, and the Brain: A Review of Impacts on Behaviour, Neurochemistry and Structure." *Central Nervous System Agents in Medicinal Chemistry (Formerly Current Medicinal Chemistry-Central Nervous System Agents)* 18, no. 3 (2018): 173-192.
 13. Feld, Gordon B., Hong-Viet Ngo, Ernesto Durán, Sandra Gebhardt, Lisa Kleist, Kerstin Brugger, Andreas Fritsche, Jan Born, and Manfred Hallschmid. "The gap junction blocker larium impairs sleep-dependent declarative memory consolidation in humans." *bioRxiv* (2019): 868901. Feld, G.B., Ngo, H.V., Durán, E., Gebhardt, S., Kleist, L., Brugger, K., Fritsche, A., Born, J. and Hallschmid, M., 2019. The gap junction blocker larium impairs sleep-dependent declarative memory consolidation in humans. *bioRxiv*, p.868901.
 14. Jeanson, Tiffany, Mathieu Charveriat, and Franck Mouthon. "Use of amitriptyline for blocking brain hemichannels and method for potentiating its consequences in vivo." U.S. Patent Application 15/744,207, filed July 26, 2018. Jeanson, T., Charveriat, M. and Mouthon, F., Theranexus, 2018. *Use of amitriptyline for blocking brain hemichannels and method for potentiating its consequences in vivo*. U.S. Patent Application 15/744,207.
 15. Njouendou, Abdel J., Fanny F. Fombad, Maeghan O'Neill, Denis Zofou, Chuck Nutting, Patrick C. Ndongmo, Arnaud J. Kengne-Ouafo, Timothy G. Geary, Charles D. Mackenzie, and Samuel Wanji. "Heterogeneity in the in vitro susceptibility of *Loa loa* microfilariae to drugs commonly used in parasitological infections." *Parasites & vectors* 11, no. 1 (2018): 223.